

Are Viruses Alive or Just Biological Machines? The answers to this question have varied in time, depending on our knowledge about viruses and our definition of life. Over the past few decades, the answer has often been negative, and viruses have usually been relegated to the periphery of the living world, being mainly considered as dangerous. They have been considered by-products of cellular life, having probably originated as escaped genes from cellular organisms. Moreover, genomic studies have further revealed that most viral genes are unique, representing a vast pool of genetic diversity distinct from cellular life.

Unlike other microorganisms, viruses are nonliving organisms outside the host cell, but when they enter the host cell, they are considered living organisms. As viruses cannot metabolize, grow, or reproduce on their own, they rely entirely on infecting a host cell, hijacking its machinery to replicate. Their size is another distinguishing factor; viruses are significantly smaller, typically 20 to 300 nanometers, compared to the larger cellular microorganisms. Viruses have mainly three main components: one is genetic material, which is a nucleic acid; the other one is a protein coat considered as capsid; and an optional component, lipid envelope. DNA viruses typically replicate in the host cell's nucleus, where their DNA is transcribed into mRNA and translated into viral proteins. RNA viruses, on the other hand, replicate in the cytoplasm, with positive-sense RNA viruses acting as mRNA directly and negative-sense RNA viruses requiring RNA polymerase for transcription. The viral life cycle includes attachment to host cell receptors, entry into the cell, replication of genetic material, assembly of new viral particles, and release, often causing host cell damage.

The remarkable capacity of some viruses to adapt to new hosts and environments is highly dependent on their ability to generate de novo diversity in a short period of time. Rates of spontaneous mutation vary amply among viruses. The mutation rate of an organism is defined as the probability that a change in genetic information is passed to the next generation. In viruses, a generation is often defined as a cell infection cycle, which includes attachment to the cell surface, entry, gene expression, replication, encapsidation, and release of infectious particles. In the basis of mutation the largest differences are found between RNA viruses (positive-strand, negative-strand, and double-strand), DNA viruses (single- and double-strand), retroviruses, and

para-retroviruses. RNA viruses generally mutate faster (10^{-6} – 10^{-4} substitutions per nucleotide per cell infection) than DNA viruses (10^{-8} – 10^{-6}) due to error-prone polymerases lacking proofreading, except for coronaviruses, which have proofreading mechanisms. Not only that, Single-strand DNA viruses tend to mutate faster than double-strand DNA viruses, although this difference is based on work with bacteriophages, as no mutation rate estimates have been obtained for eukaryotic single-strand DNA viruses. Within RNA viruses, there are no obvious differences in mutation. Unfortunately, the mechanisms underlying these differences are not well understood. One possible explanation for the differences between single and double-strand viruses is that single-strand nucleic acids are more prone to oxidative deamination and other types of chemical damage. Elevated levels of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and other cellular metabolites during viral infections can induce mutations in the host cell and in the virus.

Viruses are sensitive to temperature fluctuations, which can destabilize their protein structure and genetic material. High temperatures may impair viral replication, leading to errors that cause mutations. This can either weaken the virus or introduce variations that may enhance its adaptability. In addition to that, Ultraviolet (UV) light also damages viral nucleic acids by causing chemical changes like thymine dimers in DNA or similar disruptions in RNA. These alterations interfere with accurate replication and result in mutations. Such mutations can impact a virus's ability to infect or replicate effectively, sometimes giving rise to new, more resilient strains. Additionally, host immune pressures, such as the targeting of viral surface proteins by antibodies, push viruses to mutate in order to escape immune detection, a process known as antigenic drift. These factors collectively enable viruses to evolve quickly, enhancing their ability to survive, infect, and evade host defenses.

The mutation rate itself is a trait that can evolve by natural selection, provided the existence of genetic variation for the character. Because of that most mutations have harmful fitness effects, having a too high mutation rate would be injurious. In the short term simply because (in a first approach) the population equilibrium fitness for a haploid asexual population decreases exponentially with mutation rate. In the long term, however, it can be argued that the higher the mutation rate, the more likely it is that

beneficial mutations will be produced. An optimal mutation rate, which maximizes the rate of adaptation, is reached when these opposing factors are balanced. Not only that, a necessary condition for natural selection to optimize the mutation rate is that genetic variability for mutation rate exists in RNA viruses. Indeed, evidence for this variability has been reported. On the one hand, mutator mutants have been isolated, for example, from influenza A virus and human immunodeficiency virus type 1 (HIV-1) populations. On the other hand, antimutator mutants have been repeatedly found associated with genotypes resistant to nucleoside analogues in HIV-1 and poliovirus, presumably as a selected strategy to escape from the error catastrophe. Interestingly, increases in the mutant spectrum complexity of vesicular stomatitis virus (VSV) populations obtained by adding chemical mutagens to the environment did not translate into a higher rate of adaptation. Therefore, a decrease in mutation rate could come about with little or no loss of adaptive capacity but would benefit the population by slowing the accumulation of deleterious mutations. Indeed, this notion is supported by the observation that HIV-1 clones that became resistant to lamivudine by mutations increasing reverse transcription fidelity did not pay any cost in terms of adaptability. Together, the experiments described above failed to prove that changes in mutation rate necessarily translate into changes in the rate of adaptation. It is possible that negative results are a consequence of an insufficient amount of data or that the environments tested were too limited.

Viruses, straddling the line between life and nonlife, demonstrate extraordinary adaptability through rapid mutations. While mutations can incur fitness costs, they are essential for viral survival and evolution. Understanding the balance between beneficial and harmful mutations is crucial for developing effective strategies to combat viral diseases and manage their impact on global health.